

FORMATION OF COMMUNICATIVE COMPETENCE

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KEY WORDS

Speech competence, in the form of a monologue, the ability to conduct a discussion, communicative competence, the act of communication, communication of information, the formation of language and speech competencies, the norms of the Russian literary language and the rules of speech culture, ways of interacting with surrounding people and events, possession of the wealth of language as a condition for successful speech activity, communicative competence means willingness to put and achieve the goal of oral and written communication.

ABSTRACT

The requirements for teaching Russian language and literature include the formation of not only linguistic, but also speech competence of students related to the culture of oral and written speech, rules and methods of using language in different speech situations.

Let's try to identify the main reasons why there are problems with mastering communicative skills - The communicative aspect of speech culture remains not fully developed. Modern textbooks still cannot sufficiently ensure the formation of speech communication skills in various life situations.

- Modern life teaches students to think and evaluate the surrounding reality independently. Their speech is often poor due to the fact that they have no need to speak more expressively and beautifully. Speech is, first of all, communication, i.e. people's understanding of each other, dialogue. But the modern technique mainly develops monologue speech, and the ability to listen and hear the interlocutor is not formed.

Thus, the main goal of pedagogical activity is the formation of language and speech competencies of students based on a communicative and activity-based approach to the learning process, allowing them to master the Russian language at a practical level.

A teacher should teach the Russian language in close connection with moral education, instill love for his country, for his loved ones through the language environment. The ability to competently build your speech at a high level is possible if you have an understanding and knowledge of how the world around us is reflected with the help of various lexical and grammatical means of language, our thoughts and feelings are expressed. How to use these tools to be understood by others, and how to

correctly understand the meaning of the speech addressed to you.

Ways to implement language and speech competence

The formation of communicative competence is a long and rather complex process. The main role is given to the lessons of the Russian language. The correlation of the subject course and the student's real speech experience, the process of acquiring knowledge about the language and the process of mastering the language is particularly difficult in teaching Russian.

What can a teacher of Russian language and literature do to ensure students' communicative competence? First of all, to create optimal conditions for the advancement of each student in the educational space. To do this, it is necessary to know the educational capabilities of students. In the classroom, special attention should be paid to communicative competencies based on working with text.

The concept of communicative competence includes not only mastering the necessary set of speech and language knowledge, but also the formation of skills in the field of practical use of language in the process of speech activity. This correlates with the implementation of educational tasks for the formation of a socially active personality, oriented in the modern world. Communicative competence here it becomes part of cultural competence, leads to an increase in the general humanitarian culture of the individual, the formation of high creative, ideological and behavioral qualities necessary for its inclusion in a variety of activities.

The ways of implementing the communicative competence of students consist in the fact that the forms, methods and techniques of work are aimed at ensuring that the content of the educational material is a source for an independent search for a solution to the problem. The forms, methods and techniques of work are aimed at ensuring that the content of the educational material is a source for an independent search for a solution to the problem. In this regard, the use of innovative pedagogical technologies plays an important role. Research method, discussions brainstorming, technology of "critical thinking", interactive, group forms and methods, collective way of learning. These technologies develop creative activity, form mental activity, teach schoolchildren to defend their point of view, help to achieve a deep understanding of the material.

Working in pairs, in groups of shift staff allows you to solve the tasks of education: the desire and ability to cooperate in groups with classmates. The main thing in the work is that students speak freely, argue, defend their point of view, look for ways to solve the problem, and do not wait for ready answers. Methods focused on oral communication

- All kinds of retelling m
- All forms of educational dialogue
- Reports and communications

- Role-playing and business games • Educational research and educational projects requiring surveys
- Discussion, discussion, dispute
- Speaking as presenters at events Methods focused on written communication
- Essays and expositions
- Telecommunication texts, messages
- Participation in essay competitions

Approaches to learning:

a) competence-based approach in teaching. Successful application of this approach in teaching means that students know the language, demonstrate communication skills and are able to successfully operate outside of college, i.e. in the real world. b) the activity approach.

This approach is the basis for the formation of communicative competence, as it ensures the independent creative activity of each student. The approach is based on the position of P. Ya. Galperin that in the independent creative activity of each student it is necessary to go from external practical material actions to internal, theoretical, ideal actions. E. training assumes at the first stage joint educational and cognitive activity under the guidance of a teacher, and then - independent. We are talking about the "zone of immediate development", which must be taken into account when forming communicative competence. Conditions for the formation of communicative competence

In order for the formation of communicative competence to be effective, more successful, in order to create optimal conditions for the advancement of each student, it is necessary to know the educational capabilities of students. When determining the educational opportunities of students, two parameters are taken into account:

a) learning ability and academic performance. (One of the criteria for determining the level of training is grades in journals. The level of formation of intellectual skills is determined in the process of cognitive activity by observation. After determining the levels of formation of these qualities, the overall level of learning ability of each student is established.

b) the level of academic performance (determined by monitoring the physical performance of students, the formation of a positive attitude to learning. After determining the levels of formation of these qualities, the educational capabilities of each are established).

Content that ensures the formation of communicative competence:

- Speech and speech communication. Speech is oral and written, monological (narration, description, reasoning, a combination of types of monologue) and dialogical.
- Speech activity.

Types of speech activity: reading, listening (listening), speaking, writing. Understanding the information of the text, transmitting the content. Presentation of the content of the listened or read text (detailed, concise, selective). Creation of oral and written monological and dialogical statements of different communicative orientation.

- Text. Text as a speech work. Theme, microtheme. Types of text processing (plan, synopsis, abstract). Text analysis.
- Functional varieties of the language. Speech styles, sphere of use, stylistic genres.

Formation of communicative universal educational actions.

The formation of communicative universal educational actions is an integral part of language education at school. Language competence presupposes knowledge of the language itself, its structure and functioning, language norms, including spelling and punctuation.

In my opinion, it is the application of communicative competence in Russian language lessons that creates conditions for the development of an intellectual, creatively gifted, moral personality capable of communicating in any cultural space. Without the development of communicative competence, there can be no competitive, tolerant personality, because students develop practical skills.

The ability to engage in verbal communication, participate in a dialogue (to understand the point of view of the interlocutor, to recognize the right to a different opinion); the creation of written statements that adequately convey the listened and read information with a given degree of convolution (briefly, selectively, fully); drawing up a plan, theses, summary; giving examples, selection of arguments, formulation of conclusions; reflection in oral or written form of the results of their activities.

The ability to paraphrase a thought (to explain "in other words"); the choice and use of expressive means of language and sign systems (text, table, diagram, audiovisual series, etc.) in accordance with the communicative task, sphere and situation of communication. The use of various sources of information for solving cognitive and communicative tasks, including encyclopedias, dictionaries, Internet resources and other databases.

In Russian language lessons, I offer students various types of tasks that allow them to express their thoughts coherently and adequately, to build communicative and expedient statements in oral and written form, using the necessary language means in accordance with the purpose, content of speech and conditions of communication. This is it means that it is necessary to develop a sense of language, to develop analytical and creative abilities of students – both at the level of content and at the level of language means, which is very closely interrelated.

The formation of communicative and linguistic competencies in Russian language and literature classes occurs during the teacher's dialogue with students, when asking questions to the interlocutor, constructing an answer to a question, in a polylogue (collective discussion), in the role-playing form of presenting the text of the work. Language competence is formed in students when writing, compiling documentation, while spelling and punctuation literacy develops, speech develops that takes into account orthoepic norms, its expressiveness and emotionality.

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